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Unmanned aerial vehicles in logistics: international experience

KEYWORDS

UAV,
drone,
logistics,
goods delivery,
warehouse,
logistics process,
logistics optimization,
UAV usage restrictions,
new technologies.

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in logistics is relevant for accelerating deliveries, reducing costs, improving efficiency, and ensuring access to hard-to-reach areas.

This study is aimed at examining case studies of UAV use by various companies and identifying the advantages and disadvantages of utilizing these systems in logistics.

Materials and methods. The study used the following materials: scientific publications and articles in logistics and unmanned technologies from reputable journals; legislative and regulatory acts governing UAV use in different countries. The research methods included SWOT analysis and case study method.

Results. The experience of foreign and Russian companies using UAVs in logistics is being considered and compared. A SWOT analysis is conducted to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of UAV implementation. Additionally, given the numerous current restrictions and prohibitions on this technology, the limitations and challenges of drone use in logistics are highlighted. UAVs enable companies to reduce costs, minimize human error, and enhance efficiency through process automation. They facilitate process optimization and improvement of logistics operations within enterprises. UAVs represent the future not only of logistics but also of the broader technological sector. As businesses scale up, each company seeks to develop innovative technologies that attract customers and differentiate their operations. The adoption of drones could serve as a tool for companies not only to enhance their activities through optimization and modernization but also to increase brand recognition and operational scale.

Conclusion. The use of UAVs may contribute to reduced emissions, as they can be more energy-efficient than traditional transport vehicles. Implementing UAVs in logistics could create new jobs in development, manufacturing, maintenance, and operation, while also fostering growth in related industries.

FOR CITATION

Received: Mar 2, 2024
Accepted: Jun 6, 2024
Published: Sep 1, 2024

Lunina, E. S., Ermakov, I. A., & Satmurzaev, A. A. (2024). Unmanned aerial vehicles in logistics: international experience. *Economic Consultant*, (3), 17–29. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2024.3.2>

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the study stems from the fact that modern unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are becoming increasingly advanced, reliable, and affordable. This opens up new opportunities for their use in logistics, including cargo delivery, traffic monitoring, and inventory management.

UAVs can significantly enhance the efficiency of logistics operations by reducing delivery times, lowering fuel costs, and optimizing routes. Additionally, these devices can serve as an effective solution for delivering goods to hard-to-reach areas, such as those with geographical or infrastructural limitations. Analyzing the experience of various countries in using UAVs for logistics will help identify best practices, successful models, and potential challenges.

UAV (also known as a drone) is a pilotless device capable of performing various aerial tasks through remote ground control or fully autonomous operation. The diversity in drone sizes and configurations ranges from small multicopter quadcopters to large multicopter or fixed-wing aircraft [1]. Their applications span military operations, reconnaissance and surveillance, cargo delivery, aerial photography, and agriculture. Drones are equipped with cameras, sensors, GPS navigation systems, and other technologies necessary for executing diverse tasks. Their history in logistics began with the emergence of early UAVs in the military sector, where they were used for reconnaissance, strikes, and other operations without a pilot onboard. As technology improved and costs decreased, their use expanded into other fields, including logistics, where adoption continues to grow. The advantages of drones include their ability to operate in hazardous or inaccessible locations, improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and minimize risks. However, for safety reasons, their use is subject to specific laws and regulations.

Commercially, they are used for cargo delivery, particularly in remote and hard-to-reach areas, where they significantly reduce delivery time and costs. They are also employed for aerial photography and videography, especially in real estate, construction, agriculture, and film production. A key advantage of drones is their ability to conduct monitoring and surveillance in dangerous or inaccessible environments without human involvement. For example, in security and reconnaissance, drones are used for border surveillance, fire monitoring, search-and-rescue operations, and other high-risk tasks. However, UAVs also face limitations and challenges, including

flight range and duration constraints, restricted airspace access, and regulatory restrictions in different countries [3]. Additionally, there are concerns regarding privacy and security, as drones can be misused for illegal surveillance or transporting prohibited items. For clarity, Figure 1 presents the percentage distribution of industries utilizing UAVs.

Figure 1 Use of UAVs in various industries
(Compiled by the authors based on [4])

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials included scientific publications and articles in the fields of logistics and unmanned technologies from authoritative peer-reviewed journals (Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems, Annals of Operations Research, Operations Management Research, Production Engineering-Research and Development, Networks and Spatial Economics, Asian Journal of Social Science Research, Journal Cybernetics and Systems Analysis, CEAS Aeronautical Journal). Legislative and regulatory acts governing the use of UAVs in various countries were also considered.

Research methods employed SWOT analysis to evaluate strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with UAV implementation in logistics, and case study method to analyze specific UAV deployment projects by international companies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the 20th century, aviation established itself as one of the most important techno-social revolutions in modern human history. UAVs are on the verge of leading the next techno-social revolution, transforming multiple domains including logistics, passenger and cargo transportation, surveillance, and more. [5]

V. Kashtanov et al. analyzed the general principles of UAV operation for various applications, including weather monitoring, wildfire detection, traffic congestion tracking, cargo transportation, and use in rescue operations. The authors described the advantages and disadvantages of using UAVs, the general architecture of communication systems, and the role of UAVs within it, as well as the general characteristics of communication channels and data transmission types [6].

G. Radzki et al. note that UAVs are increasingly being used in disaster relief operations. The authors attempted to ensure the completion of planned deliveries by a UAV fleet under changing weather conditions before battery depletion and to determine emergency return routes if missions cannot be completed [7].

D. Sánchez-Partida et al. propose solutions for delivering survival kits to humans during disasters using UAVs [8].

D. Edwards et al. argue that UAVs have the potential to significantly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of future humanitarian delivery options [9].

A. Kamat et al. analyze various barriers hindering UAV implementation in humanitarian logistics for both developed and developing countries. According to the authors, developing countries should also focus on improving technological awareness among their populations [10].

In urban environments, UAVs are used for monitoring, cargo delivery, video surveillance, and mapping. While they help improve efficiency and safety, they require compliance with airspace regulations and obstacle avoidance considerations.

According to T. Xydianou and E. Nathanail, the use of drones in urban environments has reduced carbon dioxide emissions, average package delivery times, and distribution costs. The authors believe that the lack of a legal framework is the most significant obstacle to using of drones for parcel distribution in urban environments [11].

P. Mishra and G. Singh introduced an unmanned aerial system for monitoring and regulating urban development, transportation, air quality monitoring, infrastructure, etc. One of the advantages of UAVs is their use in delivering goods, which not only

reduces road congestion but also minimizes emissions compared to traditional delivery methods [12].

In the medical field, UAVs are used for rapid delivery of medicines, blood and samples, especially to hard-to-reach areas, as well as for patient monitoring and emergency operations.

V. Iliashenko et al. analyze the application of UAV technologies in healthcare. The authors propose considering the application of such technology from the perspective of key medical functions, such as the delivery of goods (drugs), organs, and other essential items [13].

K. Gunaratne et al. propose solutions to overcome systemic inefficiencies in vaccine delivery to appropriate medical facilities in Sri Lanka [14].

S. S. Kamberi et al. study the development of biomedical UAVs and their use for transporting organs for transplantation [15].

A. Sharma et al. examine the economic feasibility of incorporating UAVs into inter-hospital drug supply chains. The results show that UAV delivery significantly reduces operating costs compared to standard options [16].

The integration of UAVs with other vehicles enables more efficient logistics, automates delivery, and expands the ability to transport goods and passengers in cities and on long-distance routes.

J. Sinnemann et al. highlight that the interaction between UAVs and mobile manipulator robots (MMRs) opens up tremendous opportunities for modern industry. The authors provide a systematic review of research on the combined use of UAVs and MMRs [17].

J. Bukhari et al. state that the coordination between UAVs and ground-based electric trucks introduces a new paradigm of zero-emission ground transportation. The authors examine challenges in utilizing zero-emission vehicles from technical, environmental, economic, and policy perspectives [18].

T. Zhu et al. propose an innovative approach where battery-electric vehicles paired with drones deliver emergency supplies in rural areas. Their results demonstrate that drone speed has a more significant impact on delivery time than the electric vehicle's range [19].

M. Azmat and S. Kummer suggest employing autonomous vehicles and UAVs to address conventional logistics and transportation challenges faced by international humanitarian organizations during relief operations [20].

UAV flight optimization involves route planning, energy consumption reduction, obstacle avoidance, and weather consideration to improve efficiency and safety.

V. P. Horbulin et al. propose mathematical models for optimizing UAV base allocation, base selection, and route formation when inspecting or servicing a set of objects under flight resource constraints [21].

H. Rienecker et al. present a comprehensive approach for computing energy-optimal flight trajectories for UAVs in urban environments [22].

R. Wang et al. that long-range distribution remains a complex challenge in UAV logistics due to energy capacity limitations. The authors propose an optimization algorithm that divides locations and UAV stations into multiple segments [23].

V. Chatzara et al. believe that increased UAV integration will exacerbate safety concerns regarding flights, people, property, environment, wildlife, and privacy, which must be properly addressed through appropriate laws and regulations [24].

M. Lieret et al. demonstrate the successful use of an autonomous UAV equipped with a lightweight suction grip for object interaction. The authors discuss their approach for precise localization, identification, and position assessment of individual graspable objects [25].

Thus, examining global trends in UAV logistics applications reveals common patterns and implementation specifics across different economic and geographic contexts. Research demonstrates UAV use in weather monitoring, fire detection, cargo transport, and rescue operations. UAVs are widely employed in healthcare for delivering medicines, organs, and vaccines, improving efficiency while reducing costs. The integration of UAVs with mobile robots and ground vehicles creates new opportunities for industry and eco-friendly transportation. Studies cover UAV route optimization and distribution while accounting for resource constraints, energy efficiency, and safety considerations.

RESULTS

Case studies of UAV implementation by foreign companies

First use of drones in logistics. Amazon Prime Air. The history of the first logistics drone begins in 2013, when the American company Amazon announced its ambitious project called Prime Air. The goal of the project was to design and develop UAV capable of delivering goods to customers in the shortest possible time. Prime Air was introduced on the 60 Minutes TV show featuring Amazon's founder,

Jeff Bezos. It immediately sparked great public interest. On December 7, 2016, Jeff Bezos announced to the media the first delivery using a drone. A customer from the UK ordered a TV set-top box and popcorn. The delivery took 13 minutes from the moment of order [26].

Google. Project Wings. In 2012, Alphabet Inc. (Google's parent company) initiated research into cargo delivery via UAVs. Two years later, in August 2014, Project Wing was officially announced. The project's objective was the development of an automated UAV system and corresponding logistics infrastructure for commercial parcel delivery. Google aimed to establish a service that would be adopted by third-party enterprises. Initial prototypes included multiple UAV configurations, among them a tailsitter-type fixed-wing VTOL (vertical takeoff and landing) drone. However, after several months of testing, this design was replaced with a revised model incorporating distinct propulsion systems for vertical and horizontal flight. Despite negotiations and pilot deliveries of medical supplies and food, the project failed to achieve commercial viability and was ultimately discontinued.

DHL. Parcel delivery via UAVs. DHL, a leading German logistics corporation, explored UAV-based cargo delivery solutions [6]. In 2013, the company conducted initial flight tests in Germany, followed by operational trials involving the transportation of pharmaceuticals and essential supplies to the island of Juist. In 2016, DHL executed further testing in the Bavarian Alps, deploying drones for inter-settlement deliveries [8]. Although a limited number of parcels were successfully delivered, the project did not progress beyond the experimental phase.

Zipline. Blood sample and medical supply delivery. In 2016, California-based Zipline commenced the deployment of UAVs for the transportation of blood samples and medical supplies under a partnership with the Rwandan government. Healthcare providers submitted urgent blood supply requests via SMS to a dedicated logistics hub, where personnel loaded the cargo onto UAVs for dispatch. The drones, equipped with parachute release mechanisms, delivered payloads to designated drop zones before returning autonomously to the hub. A key advantage of this system was the elimination of runway dependency and landing gear requirements. Having achieved operational success in Rwanda, the project is slated for expansion into Tanzania and the United States [27].

Matternet. Delivery of medical supplies and collaboration with Mercedes-Benz. In 2012, the American company Matternet utilized UAVs to deliver medical supplies to a refugee camp in Haiti, employing quadcopters with integrated cargo

compartments. In 2016, the company participated in a Malawian initiative for HIV/AIDS diagnostic blood sample transport, deploying an updated UAV model with a centralized cargo bay. That same year, Matternet announced a collaboration with Mercedes-Benz to develop the Vision Van, a cargo microbus equipped with UAVs for last-mile delivery. The drones were intended to deploy when the vehicle halted within proximity of the delivery zone. As of now, none of Matternet's UAV-based logistics projects have advanced beyond the developmental stage.

UPS. Post car-aircraft carrier. In February 2017, UPS unveiled a pilot program integrating delivery trucks with UAVs [6]. The trucks transported parcels to rural communities, where drones executed the final distribution to individual households. This hybrid delivery model was designed to enhance operational efficiency and reduce driver workload. The project remains in the testing phase [28].

ST Engineering. DroNet platform. In February 2022, ST Engineering launched the DroNet platform for shore-to-ship cargo delivery in Singapore. Under the pilot program, corporate partners utilized UAVs to transport payloads of up to 7 kg, including financial documents for vessel crews. ST Engineering estimates that UAVs could handle 10–20% of total shore-to-ship logistics, reducing delivery times and operational costs.

Flowcopter. At the end of February 2022, Flowcopter unveiled an innovative hydraulic UAV—the first of its kind. The design aimed to address conventional UAV limitations, such as restricted flight range and payload capacity. The Flowcopter UAV achieves flight endurance of six hours, covering distances up to 900 km, while maintaining a payload capacity of 150 kg for short-range missions. The project was inspired by the UK's Royal National Lifeboat Institution (RNLI), which sought solutions for maritime rescue operations. Currently, this UAV is the only platform meeting extreme maritime operational demands in terms of range and payload. Priced below \$1,000 per unit, the project remains under active development [29].

SWOT analysis of UAV implementation in logistics

In order to assess the advantages and disadvantages of drone utilization in logistics, the SWOT analysis framework (Table 1) can be applied. This analytical tool provides a structured evaluation of UAV deployment, identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. The insights derived from this analysis can inform strategic decision-making and enhance corporate logistics systems.

Table 1

SWOT analysis of UAV deployment in logistics

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Faster delivery times • Increased performance • Cost reduction • Simplified delivery • Improved inventory management • Minimal return logistics issues • Real-time tracking • High flexibility and maneuverability • Global coverage potential • Enhanced supply chain visibility • Reduced environmental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited payload capacity • Need for specialized infrastructure and charging networks • Weather dependency • Restricted flight range and battery limitations • Cybersecurity risks • International regulatory constraints • Maintenance and repair complexities
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Industry-wide technological innovations • Advancements in autonomous transportation • AI and machine learning integration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evolving legal and regulatory restrictions • Cargo theft and loss risks • Privacy and confidentiality concerns • Market competition

Compiled by the authors based on research data

In order to develop and determine the most precise strategy for UAV advancement in logistics, a correlation SWOT analysis is employed, as presented in Table 2. By simultaneously examining strengths and weaknesses alongside opportunities and threats, this approach provides a comprehensive understanding of the subject matter and enables the identification of optimal operational and developmental strategies.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Unmanned aerial systems possess immense potential to transform the logistics and transportation sectors. Cost reduction, enhanced safety, and improved efficiency are just a few of the many benefits they offer. However, several barriers must be overcome for widespread adoption, including regulatory challenges, high costs, and public perception.

The Russian UAV market lags significantly behind global leaders. Nevertheless, domestic companies continue to evolve, seeking ways to improve despite legislative constraints. Enterprises that successfully integrate UAVs into their operations will not only gain a competitive edge but also significantly influence the future of logistics and transportation services.

Table 2

Correlation SWOT analysis of UAV implementation in logistics

Correlation SWOT analysis		Opportunities	Threats
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry innovations Development of autonomous transportation Advancements in artificial intelligence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legislative and regulatory constraints Cargo theft and loss risks Privacy and confidentiality violations Market competition
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Faster delivery times Increased performance Cost reduction Simplified delivery Improved inventory management Minimal return logistics issues Real-time tracking Flexibility and maneuverability Global coverage potential Enhanced supply chain visibility Reduced environmental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased profitability Expansion of operational scope Entry into international markets Business scalability Reduction of human-factor errors Technological advancements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Revision of existing laws and establishment of new regulations Enhancement of cargo protection technologies Continuous technological improvements driven by market competition
	Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited payload capacity Need for specialized infrastructure solutions, power line challenges Weather dependency Restricted flight range and battery limitations Cybersecurity risks International regulatory constraints Maintenance and repair complexities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modernization of route infrastructure Development of robust security systems AI-driven route adaptation to weather conditions AI-optimized battery performance improvements

Compiled by the authors based on research data

The Russian UAV market lags significantly behind global leaders. Nevertheless, domestic companies continue to evolve, seeking ways to improve despite legislative constraints. Enterprises that successfully integrate UAVs into their operations will not only gain a competitive edge but also significantly influence the future of logistics and transportation services. Given ongoing technological advancements, the world can anticipate further breakthroughs in unmanned systems and their applications, driven by the continuous pursuit of automation and efficiency in this sector.

Thus, the prospects for the development of UAVs are obvious. They can optimize logistics processes by reducing delivery times and operational costs, particularly

in hard-to-reach areas or congested urban environments. UAV deployment may also contribute to lower emissions, as they can be more energy-efficient than conventional transportation methods. Additionally, drones can facilitate cargo delivery to remote or inaccessible regions where traditional logistics are inefficient or prohibitively expensive. UAVs can also enhance inventory management, real-time goods monitoring, and warehouse optimization, improving overall supply chain efficiency. Furthermore, their integration into logistics may generate new employment opportunities in UAV development, manufacturing, maintenance, and operations, while stimulating growth in related industries.

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The authors have declared that no competing interests exist

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Editor: Eduard A. Sosnin. National Reseach Tomsk State University (Russia)